

CHARACTERIZATION OF THE DIFFUSIBLE SIGNALING FACTOR OF *XYLELLA FASTIDIOSA* CODIRO STRAIN

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Recent studies demonstrated that the virulence of *Xylella fastidiosa* relies on a fine balance between more motile bacterial forms, able to move and proliferate within xylem vessels, and sticky cells forming a biofilm, which are responsible for vessels blockage and insect acquisition. This different behavior is regulated in a cell density-dependent manner by diffusible signaling factors (DSFs), produced by the *rpfF* gene that initiates a transduction cascade resulting in up- or down-regulation of several genes. Mainly DSFs identified in *Xf* subspecies *fastidiosa* and having biological activity, consist of 2-cis unsaturated fatty acids and particularly a 2-tetradecenoic (*Xf*DSF1) and a 2-hexadecanoic acid (*Xf*DSF2). The characterization of these molecules has a direct application in a "pathogen confusion" strategy for reducing the impact of *Xf*-infections since the approach consists in tricking the pathogen, by altering DSF level *in planta* and lowering its virulence.

DSFs produced by the CoDiRO strain of *Xf* were extracted from bacterial culture media with equal volumes of ethyl acetate (EtOAc). The EtOAc fractions, after drying over Na₂SO₄, were analyzed by Gas Chromatography -Mass Spectrometry analysis. Preliminary results showed that a family of unsaturated fatty acids with a chain length of 12-18 carbon atoms is produced. Their further full characterization and principally localization of the unsaturated bond is in progress by ¹H nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) and ¹³C NMR spectra.